

International Seminar
Advances In Food Bio-Preservation
2-4 October 2022

International Seminar

Advances In Food Bio-Preservation, ISAFP, 2022

Tunis Science City, Tunisia, 2nd -4th, October 2022

Pre-Seminar Booklet, version 28/09/2022

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2nd - 4th October at Tunis Science City, Tunisia

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1. PREFACE

ARTISANEFOOD-2019-2023 project is a PRIMA-funded project aiming to develop simple, efficient and /or innovative bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, targeting the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in artisanal fermented foods with meat or dairy origin.

The International Seminar “Advances in Food Bio-preservation, ISAFBP 2022” is organized in the framework of ArtiSaneFood project. It offers the opportunity for researchers and PhD students to present their research results dealing with the application of natural food preservatives and biocontrol interventions of food (using natural plant extracts and/or lactic acid bacteria, LAB). Multifunctional properties (*in vitro* and *in vivo* assays) of biomolecules recovered from agro-industrial waste and those of LAB were also underlined through a special communication session. Three-minute E-Poster pitches session will be organized for selected posters. ISAFBP 2022 is also an opportunity to attend a fully practical workshop dealing with classic and dynamic modelling in predictive microbiology. The workshop features prominent experts in the field: Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron & Vasco Cadavez, from the Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza, Portugal.

We are grateful to all our colleagues from LR- Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules (ISBST, UMA), LR Livestock and Wildlife IRA Mednine (UG), LR, PATIO (INAT, UCAR), Post-Doc and PhD students for their valuable collaboration. Many thanks to Prof. ElHatmi H, Prof. Hammadi M, Prof. Khorchani, T and Prof. Ben Chaoucha Chekir, R for helping with organization ISAFBP 2022 and making it an interesting event for sharing valuable scientific results between researchers. Many thanks to Dr. Malek BenZid for significant contribution to seminar preparation since June 2022, to Dr. M’hiri Nouha and Prof. Maha Benlarbi for contribution to English reviewing of the booklet.

A special thank to Prof. Fethi Zagrouba (PDG, Tunis Science City, TSC, Tunisia) and all the team of CST for their availability, collaboration and for offering us a guided visits to TSC and to the Planetarium.

The final seminar of ARTISANEFOOD is programmed in May 2023 at The last seminar is to be held in the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança and will be another opportunity to meet in-person with all project partners. You can continue to follow ARTISANEFOOD project via the following links:

<http://ipb.pt/artisanefood/>; <https://facebook.com/artisanefood>.

On behalf of steering and organizing committees, Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua,

Artisanefood Project Lead for Tunisian Team

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2. PROJECT PRESENTATION

ARTISANEFOOD PROJECT: to increase food safety in artisanal fermented milk and dried meat and sausage

Title: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

Acronym: ARTISANEFOOD

Budget: 1.583708 €

Period: 36 months (to be achieved May 2023)

Call: PRIMA-S2-2018-PIC2019

Number: PRIMA/0001/2018

AIMS

The main object of this project is to develop efficient bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, aiming to the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in 15 artisanal fermented foods of meat or dairy origin produced in Portugal, Spain, Italy, France, Greece, Morocco and Tunisia.

It consists of an integrated risk-based approach sustained by the concepts of:

- (i) extensive tracking surveys in the artisanal food chains, in order to identify origin, routes of contamination, risk factors favouring pathogens' survival, and technological causes for lack of homogeneity in the quality/safety of end-products;
- (ii) biopreservation, whereby functional starter cultures and natural extracts will be assessed as extra hurdles to ensure safety and extend shelf-life;
- (iii) fate studies of pathogens, predictive dynamic modelling,
- (iv) risk process modelling, for the delineation of the most effective biointerventions, optimisation of process variables and norms/standards, and design of quality monitoring tools.

14h30-18h30	Classical versus dynamic modelling in predictive microbiology – Practice using R	Dr. Vasco Cadavez
4th October 2022		
8h00-9h30	O2. Omnibus and microbial competition models – Theory (<i>Key-lecture</i>)	Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron
9h30-10h00	Q/R Session Poster Pitches Session 2: E-Poster 14 to E-Poster 29	
10h00-10h30	Coffee Break	
LACTIC ACID BACTERIA & FOOD BIOPRESERVATION MODERATORS: PROF. HAMMADI, M PROF. KORCHANI T.		
10h30-10h40	O14. Characterization of traditional Tunisian arid zone fermented goat milk, Rayeb, using <i>Enterococcus faecium</i> isolated from dromedary-fermented milk	Khaoula Belguith
10h40-10h50	O15. Photosensitization effect of thyme essential oil for controlling plant pathogen <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> and <i>Alternaria alternata</i> in postharvest tomatoes	Dhekraa Trabelsi
10h50-11h00	O16. Effect of enzymatic hydrolysis on antioxidant activities of milk whey proteins from five different species	Meriem Ben Yagoub
11h10-11h20	O17. Camel milk casein as a potent source of natural antioxidant peptides	Zeineb Jrad
11h20-11h30	O18. Camel skim milk fermented by newly isolated autochthonous probiotic <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> : Quality characteristics and anti-obesity properties	Oufa Oussaief
11h30-11h40	O19. Anti-tumoral activity of <i>Allium roseum</i> compounds on Breast cancer cells MCF7 and MDA-MB231	Yosr Haffani
11h40-11h50	O20. How does dietary pomegranate peels incorporated in concentrate pellets affect lambs' meat quality and shelf life?	Hadhami Hajji
11h50-12h00	O21. Biological control methods against ochratoxin A-producing fungi isolated from grapes	Islem Dammak
12h00-12h15	Q/R Session	
12h15-13h15	Omnibus and microbial competition models – Practice using R	Dr. Vasco Cadavez
13h15-14h00	Lunch	
SPECIAL SESSION: Multi-functional biomolecules from agro-industrial waste: food bio-preservatives, antioxidants, <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> antidiabetic and anti-tumoral properties		
MODERATORS: PROF. HANEN NAJAA , PROF ESSID I, PROF. SIHEM BELLAGHA		
14h05-14h20	O22. Effects of antioxidant biomolecules extracted from agro-industrial byproducts on the prevention of diabetes and diabetic Retinopathy in Tunisian <i>Psammomys obesus</i> model (<i>Key-lecture</i>)	Prof. Rafika Ben Chaouacha-Chekir
14h20-14h30	O23. Anti -diabetic activity of camel milk; findings in pancreatic beta cells	Amel Sboui
14h30-14h40	O24. Effects of olive mill wastewater compound on retinal function and astroglial glutamate metabolic networks in Diabetic	Oumaima Achour

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	Retinopathy <i>Psammomys obesus</i>	
14h40-14h50	O25. Effect of a biomolecule extracted from brown algae on molecular and cellular alterations in diabetic <i>Psammomys obesus</i> at the retinal and systemic level	Oumayma Hammami
14h50-15h00	O26. Evaluation of anti-hyperlipidemic effect and antioxidant activities of carotenoids extracted from halophilic <i>Archaea</i> – Case study of hyperlipidemic mice	Sana Ben Hamad Bouhamed
15h00-15h30	<p>Q/R Session</p> <p>Winner announcement for Poster Pitches Session , Round table discussion & Miscellaneous session</p>	
15h30-17h00	Guided visit to Tunis Science City of and to the Planetarium	Interested participants

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4. SCIENTIFIC & STEERING COMMITTEES

Scientific committee

Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua, ISBST, UMA, TN
Prof. Halima El-Hatmi, ISBAM & IRA, TN
Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron, CIMO-IPB, PT
Dr. Vasco Cadavez, CIMO-IPB, PT
Dr. Tenenhaus-Aziza Fanny, CNIEL, FR
Dr Alessendra De Cesare, Université de Bologne, IT
Prof. Antonio Valero, Université Cordoba, ES
Prof. Fouad, Achemchem, UIZ, MA
Dr. Khaoula Belguith, ISBST, UMA, TN
Prof. Khorchani Touhami, IRA, TN
Prof. Mohamed Hammadi, IRA, TN
Prof. Rafika BenChaoucha Chekir, ISBST, UMA, TN
Prof. Sihem Bellagha, INAT, UCAR, TN
Prof. Iness Essid, INAT, UCAR, TN
Prof. Hanen Najaa, IRA, TN
Dr. Amel Sboui, IRA, TN
D.r Yosr Haffani, ISBST, UMA, TN
Prof. Maha BenLarbi, ISBST, UMA, TN
Dr. Ridha Ghali, UMA, TN

Steering committee

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Dr Malek Benzid, ISBST, UMA, TN
Prof. Mohamed Hammadi, IRA, TN
Prof. Touhami Khorchani, IRA, TN
Prof. Halima El-Hatmi, ISBAM & IRA, TN
Dr. Zeineb Jrad, IRA, TN
Dr. Olfa Loussaif, IRA, TN
Dr. Nouha M'hiri, ISBST, UMA, TN
Dr. Nesrine Rokbeni, ISBST, UMA, TN
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Ms. Ibtissem BenHmidène, ISBST, UMA, TN
Mr.Mohamed Dbara, IRA, TN
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Mr. Mabrouk Lanouar, IRA, TN
Mr. Mourad Smida, IRA, TN
Mr. Soufiane Errich, IRA, TN
Mr. Chokri Khorchani, IRA, TN
Ms. Raida Ben Siff, IRA, TN

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5. ABSTRACTS

Abstract N°: 01 (O1)

CLASSICAL VERSUS DYNAMIC MODELLING IN PREDICTIVE MICROBIOLOGY

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Predictive microbiology is a field within Food Microbiology, which integrates knowledge on microbiology, engineering, mathematics and information technology, in order to describe the behaviour of microorganisms in food. Predictive microbiology has become a discipline of emergent development and intervention, and comprises two types of modelling: the classical two-step modelling and the dynamic modelling.

Classical modelling entails the adjustment of kinetic primary models to data obtained under fixed or constant environmental conditions, followed by the adjustment of secondary models used to describe the effect of environmental conditions on the kinetic parameters of microorganisms. On the other hand, dynamic models are predictive microbiology models that are adjusted to data obtained under changing environmental conditions; ex. changing temperature, pH. While classical predictive microbiology models are relatively simple to fit as explicit equations, dynamic models require a greater mathematical knowledge since implicit equations must be solved using ordinary differential equations. In this talk, the necessary theoretical background of both types of models will be presented as well as application examples of actual predictive microbiology problems.

Key words: Primary model; Secondary model; Static experiments; Dynamic experiments

Supporting Fund: The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021). The authors are also grateful to the EU PRIMA programme, the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for funding the ArtiSaneFood project (PRIMA/0001/2018).

Abstract N°: 03 (O3)

***Myrtus communis* Essential Oil: Chemical Composition and Antimicrobial Activities against Food Spoilage Pathogens**

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Myrtus communis is a typical plant of the Mediterranean area, which is mainly used as animal and human food and in folk medicine for treating some disorder diseases. In the present study, we evaluated *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal properties of the essential oils of *Myrtus communis* (McEO) as well as its phytochemical composition. The GC-MS analysis of the essential oil revealed 17 compounds. 1.8-cineol (16.55%), Linalool (13.30%), α -terpineol (2.88%), α -pinene (15.59%), Limonene (8.94%), Myrtenyl acetate (20.75%), Linalyl acetate (3.67%), Geranyl acetate (2.99%), Methyl eugenol (1.17%), and α -humulene (1.29%) were identified as the major components. The antimicrobial activity of the essential oil was also investigated on several microorganisms. The inhibition zones and minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of bacterial strains were in the range of 16-28 mm and 0.078-2.5 mg/ml, respectively. The inhibitory activity of the McEO against Gram-positive bacteria was significantly higher than against Gram-negative. It also exhibited remarkable activity against several fungal strains. The investigation of the mode of action of the McEO by the time-kill curve against *Listeria monocytogenes* (food isolate 2132) showed a drastic bactericidal effect after 5 min using a concentration of 312 μ g/ml. These results suggest that the McEO possesses antimicrobial properties, and is therefore a potential source of active ingredients for food and pharmaceutical industries.

Key words: *Myrtus communis*, Essential oil, GC/MS, Antibacterial; Antifungal activities.

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Abstract N°: 04 (O4)

From modeling and optimizing extraction of peels beetroot (*Beta vulgaris* L.) betalains to in silico probing of their antibacterial multitarget mechanisms

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The heartening applications of betalains in food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic sectors impose their strengthening by a suit able extraction protocol. Likewise, the antibacterial activity of beetroot betalains represents an option to develop the next generation of antibacterial agents treating the wide bacterial infection spectrum. This study aimed to model and optimize the ethanolic extract of beetroot peels in betacyanin (Bc) and betaxanthin (Bx) and their activity against two foodborne pathogen bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella enterica*) by using RSM (response surface methodology) and ANN (artificial neural network). The input variables considered were sample-to-solvent ratio, temperature, and extraction time. The higher Bc (5.87 g/L) and Bx (10.18 g/L) contents, and anti-*Staphylococcus aureus* (17.52 mm) and anti-*Salmonella enterica* (15.14 mm) activities were recorded at: sample-to-solvent ratio of 1:36, temperature of 44.54 °C, and extraction time equal to 93.03 min. Statistical analyses indicated that the models derived using RSM and ANN can be used to predict each response. Based on the coefficient of determination and mean square error, ANN model was found to be superior compared to RSM in the prediction of all responses. Molecular docking simulation stipulated that Bc and Bx could target multiple bacterial pathways including membrane permeability disruption by inhibiting MepR and AcrB efux pump of *S. aureus* and *S. enterica* respectively. Both bioactive molecules showed a conceivable impairment of pathogenic bacteria replication and transcription vital processes by impeding DNA and RNA polymerase activities. These findings indicated that beet peel extracts can provide an excellent source of betalains for the color industry.

Keywords: Beta vulgaris L.; Betalains; Optimization; Molecular docking; Replication and transcription inhibition; Membrane permeability.

Abstract N°: 06 (O6)

Olive and olive oil by-products for the development of active packaging materials to extend oil shelf life (VIPack): protective effect of olive leaves extract incorporated in sunflower oil

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VIPack seeks to provide technologically and economically viable and environmentally friendly approaches based on olive and olive oil by-products for the recovery of stable and active ingredients destined to produce active packaging materials to extend the shelf life and improve the quality and safety of vegetable oils. The purpose of this preliminary study is to evaluate the capacity of olive leaves extract (OLE) in improving the overall oxidative stability of commercial sunflower oil (SFO). OLE obtained by ultrasound-assisted extraction was first characterized for its major phenolic compounds by high performance liquid chromatography coupled to diode array UV detector (HPLC-DAD) and for its antioxidant capacity (FRAP, DPPH and H₂O₂ scavenging assays). SFO batches supplemented with 0.1, 0.25 and 0.5% OLE (w: v) were monitored for their composition and quality parameters under accelerated thermal oxidation (70°C for 1 week). The results showed that OLE contained simple phenols (hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol), secoiridoids (verbascoside, oleuropein), flavonols (quercetin, rutin) and phenolic acids (caffeic acid, *p*-coumaric acid). Oleuropein was the major phenolic component of the extract with an average concentration of 20 mg/ g OLE. OLE achieved DPPH antiradical, H₂O₂ scavenging and reducing power with TEAC values of 0.32, 0.24 and 0.25 mg Trolox equivalent / g of extract, respectively. Starting from the 0.25% OLE concentration, free acidity and peroxide value of SFO dropped by a factor of 1.5 to 2 folds compared to the control. However, conjugated dienes content remained unchanged for the three doses of OLE. These results show that OLE acts at the early stages of lipid degradation by inhibiting free fatty acids generation. This study shows that OLE could be used as a natural and safe additive to mitigate oil quality deterioration during storage.

Keywords: olive leaves extract, lipid peroxidation, food preservation

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by the VIPack project (TUNGER 18-001) (2021-2023) which is funded by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR, Tunisia) through the Tunisian – German bilateral S & T cooperation involving science and industry (2+2 projects).

Abstract N°: 07 (O7)

S. aureus inactivation in goat's milk at sub-pasteurisation temperatures

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In the manufacture of traditional cheeses, replacing raw milk with heat-treated milk can minimise the number of pathogens in the final product, for example, *S. aureus* (SA). However, minimally heat-treated milk must be used so that cheeses maintain the same characteristics as those made from raw milk. To this end, thermisation can be used, a heat treatment that uses temperatures lower than those of pasteurisation, while still reducing the bacterial counts. Hence, the aim of our work was to characterize the heat resistance of SA in milk at sub-pasteurisation temperatures using a non-linear inactivation model.

Five mL of milk were placed in sample bags and inoculated with SA (7 log CFU/mL). The inactivation experiments were carried out in a water bath at 55, 58, 61 and 64 °C, and the sampling was performed at appropriate times. After removing the samples from the water bath, they were immersed into an ice bath. Upon cooling, SA determination was performed. SA decay behaviour was modelled by a modified Weibull equation, defined as: $Y(t) = Y_0 - \left(\frac{t}{\chi}\right)^\beta$.

Significant effects ($p < 0.01$) were observed concerning SA kinetics in heat-treated milk. The estimated χ (min⁻¹) and β (dimensionless) were 37.87 ± 1.46 and 2.22 ± 0.17 , for 55 °C; 9.68 ± 1.02 and 1.14 ± 0.09 , for 58 °C; 0.57 ± 0.18 and 0.63 ± 0.07 , for 61 °C; and 0.46 ± 0.04 and 1.13 ± 0.06 , for 64 °C.

The decrease of β as the temperature applied increased implies that thermisation caused increasingly more damage to SA. Moreover, β values higher than 1 suggest that the surviving cells become increasingly damaged, whereas β values lower than 1 suggest that the remaining cells can adapt to the applied heat stress.

Using a non-linear model, this work characterised the heat resistance of SA in milk at sub-pasteurisation temperatures and demonstrated that thermisation can be used to reduce SA counts.

Key words: Weibull, thermisation, cheesemaking, milk treatment, modelling

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood (PRIMA/0001/2018): Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods, funded by the EU PRIMA program and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal). The authors are grateful to FCT for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021). This study was supported by FCT under the scope of the strategic funding of UIDB/04469/2020 unit and Bio-TecNorte operation (NORTE-01-0145-FEDER-000004) funded by the European Regional Development Fund under the scope of Norte2020—Programa Operacional Regional do Norte.

Abstract N°: 08 (O8)

Molecular and phenotypic features of lactic acid producing bacteria isolated from Alheira –Portuguese traditional meat product

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Portuguese traditional fermented meat products constitute a valued economic and cultural heritage strongly linked to the identity of the population and to their production areas. The objective of this work was to screen the lactic acid bacteria (LAB) present in alheira - a traditional fermented sausage. Alheiras from different regions of Trás-os-Montes (Bragança, Mirandela, Vimioso, Mogadouro, Vinhais and Valpaços) were isolated and identified by Sanger sequencing of the 16S ribosomal gene region. A total of 17 LAB isolates were characterised in terms of in-vitro antimicrobial capacities against pathogens, acidification potential, production of L-lactic acid and proteolytic activity. Genomic DNA of the samples was extracted, and the primers used for amplification of the 16S rRNA gene were 27f 5'-AGA GTT TGA TCC TGG CTC AG-3' and 1492r 5'-CTA CGG CTA CCT TGT TAC GA-3'. Sequencing reactions used BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 while purification of samples used SAM/BigDyeXTerminator™ bead solution. Capillary electrophoresis was run in SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer. Sequence results were aligned with sequences from the NCBI database, alignments of at least $\leq 85\%$ identity were obtained using the BLAST algorithm. Data was assessed by Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Genetic analysis of samples showed a diverse lactic acid producing microbiome. LABs from the genus *Lactobacillus* and *Leuconostoc* were dominant, found in 64% of samples, while organisms of the genus *Streptococcus* and *Enterococcus* were found in 36% of samples. *Lactobacillus*, *Pediococcus* and *Leuconostoc* presented overall higher inhibition diameters against *Listeria monocytogenes* (PC1=58.2%, PC2=81.6%), *Salmonella typhimurium* (PC1=61.5%, PC2=86%) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (PC1=61%, PC2=85.7%). *Enterococcus* and *Streptococcus* tended to produce higher acidification. L-(+)-lactic acid production was higher in *Lactobacillus*. This work enabled the identification of LAB normally present in a traditional Portuguese product, as well as the desired technological characteristics that they can bestow to the product.

Key words: microbial population diversity, food quality, food biotechnology, microbiome, fermented sausages

Supporting Fund: The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021). The authors are also grateful to the EU PRIMA programme, the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for funding the ArtiSaneFood project (PRIMA/0001/2018).

Abstract N°: 9 (O9)

Thermal resistant parameters of *Salmonella Typhimurium* in alheira sausage batter

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Previous studies have highlighted the need to implement better microbiological control and process standardization during the production of alheiras sausages, in particular during the stage of heat treatment. Alheira is a non-ready-to-eat sausage from Northern Portugal, which although at low prevalence, has shown survivability of *Salmonella* spp. throughout maturation. The objective of this work was to characterize the heat resistance of *Salmonella Typhimurium* (ST) in alheira sausage batter.

Two batches of alheira batter were obtained from a producer and inoculated with a ST overnight culture to reach ~ 7.0 log CFU/g. Bags containing well-spread 10-g alheira batter were submitted in duplicate to temperatures of 63°, 60°, 57° and 54 °C in an immersion bath, and sampled at 6 different time points. The quantification of ST on XLD plates was performed within two hours of the experiment.

A log-linear primary model fitted to each of the inactivation curves estimated the death rates of ST in alheira batter to be 0.038 (SE=0.008), 0.126 (SE=0.003), 0.273 (SE=0.063) and 2.872 (SE=0.763) log CFU/min at 54 °, 57 °, 60 ° and 63 °C, respectively, with coefficients of determination ranging between 0.914 and 0.987. Through a Bigelow model, the D-value (time needed to reduce ST in 1 log) was modelled as a function of temperature, resulting in a log D* of 2.302 (SE=0.304), corresponding to 200 minutes at 50 °C to reduce ST in 1 log, and a z-value of 5.016 (SE=0.839) °C. This model enables the prediction of D values and lethality times at other temperatures. For instance, to reach the 7.0 log reduction lethality of *Salmonella* spp. sought in sausages, the center of the alheiras should be kept for 9.0 seconds at 70 °C.

This study characterized for the first time the thermal kinetic parameters of a traditional Portuguese sausage and will be useful to producers for designing and controlling their thermal processes during alheira manufacture.

Key words: Foodborne pathogens; predictive microbiology; modelling; artisanal product; D value.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood (PRIMA/0001/2018): Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods, funded by the EU PRIMA program and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal). The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021). The authors are also grateful to the EU PRIMA programme, the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for funding the Arti-SaneFood project (PRIMA/0001/2018).

Abstract N°: 10 (O10)

Camel Kefir: Processing, composition and evolution of kefir grain weight during fermentation

Arroum, S. (1, 2); Lazrag A. (3); Sboui, A. (1); Fguiri, I. (1); Ayeb, N. (1); Hammadi, M.(1); Khorchani T.(1)

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This study aimed to transform camel milk into kefir using kefir grains (5%, during 24 hour) and to follow the evolution of the kefir grain during this process. The physicochemical composition and microbiological parameters of kefir were analyzed. The pH, acidity and viscosity for camel kefir were $(4.64 \pm 0.51, 70 \pm 2.83 \text{ }^\circ\text{D}, 51.43 \pm 0.49 \text{ cP})$ respectively. The gross composition of this product was also determined and showed $31.57 \pm 0.3 \text{ g/l}$ for fat content, $22.4 \pm 0.42 \text{ g/l}$ for proteins, $105.02 \pm 1.23 \text{ g/l}$ as dry matter concentration and $8.52 \pm 0.69 \text{ g/l}$ for the mineral matter level. Microbiological composition of camel kefir demonstrated $32 \times 10^5 \text{ UFC/ml}$ as lactic acid bacteria content and $7.5 \times 10^5 \text{ UFC/ml}$ for yeasts and molds.

The daily evolution of kefir grains in camel milk during fermentation was also followed. These results showed that the grains grow up from 10 g to 15.5 g (55%) during 15 days. This increase in kefir grain weight showed an effect on pH, acidity, viscosity and dry matter of the obtained kefir.

Key words: kefir, kefir grain, camel milk.

Abstract N°: 11 (O11)

Nutritional, antimicrobial and medicinal properties of Camel milk proteins

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Camel's milk is an important part of staple diet in several parts of the world, particularly in the arid and semi-arid zones. Camel milk is traditionally consumed as a fresh or naturally fermented product. Within the last couple of years, an increasing quantity is being processed in dairy plants, and a number of consumer products have been marketed. A better understanding of the technological and functional properties, as required for product improvement, has been gained in the past years. Absence of whey β -LG and a low proportion of κ -casein cause differences in relation to dairy processing. Proposed health benefits include inhibition of the angiotensin converting enzyme, antimicrobial and antioxidant properties as antidiabetogenic effect. Camel's milk is rich in health-beneficial substances, such as bioactive peptides, lactoferrin, zinc, and mono and polyunsaturated fatty acids. These substances could help in the treatment of some important human diseases like tuberculosis, asthma, gastrointestinal diseases, and jaundice. Camel's milk composition is more variable compared to cow's milk. The effects of feed, breed, age, and lactation stage on milk composition are more significant in camel. Region and season significantly change the ratio of compounds in camel's milk. In addition to their high nutritional value and technological properties, there are also implications for human nutrition and camel milk proteins are of interest for application in infant food, for food preservation and in functional food. These whey proteins have unique characteristics, including physical, chemical, physiological, functional, and technological features that are useful in the food application. The hydrolysis of camel's milk proteins leads to the formation of bioactive peptides, which affect major organ systems of the body and impart physiological functions to these systems. The camel's milk has antioxidant, antimicrobial, angiotensin-I-converting enzyme (ACE)-inhibitory peptides, antidiabetic as well as anticholesterol activities.

Keywords: Camel Milk; Health; Nutrition; Whey Protein, technological properties.

Abstract N°: 12 (O12)

Inhibitory effect of an essential oil on the growth of *Aspergillus niger* on Wheat seeds

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Wheat seeds during storage are exposed to many spoilage agents (insects, mold, mites, etc.). Mycotoxigenic fungi are very important spoilage agents by secreting secondary metabolites that are highly toxic to humans and animals. The use of physical and chemical methods for the control of fungi and their mycotoxins has been restricted for health safety reasons, which made it necessary to find safe and effective ways to combat this pest. In addition, the treatment should be inexpensive without changing the nutritional value of the food. This study was designed to evaluate the inhibitory effects of some essential oils (EOs) extracted from aromatic plants on the growth of pathogenic fungi *Aspergillus niger* isolated from wheat seeds.

The EOs were obtained by hydrodistillation from four aromatic plants *Thymus capitatus*, *Origanum onites*, *Laurus nobilis* and *Menthe Pouliot*. The phytochemical analysis was carried out by gas chromatography associated with time-of-flight mass spectrometry. The antifungal activity of EOs was performed by the agar dilution method on Czapek Yeast extract Agar medium (agar diffusion technique). The production of ochratoxin A (OTA) by *Aspergillus niger* was determined by liquid chromatography with a fluorescence detector (HPLC/FLD).

The results obtained revealed that the isolated strain is an OTA producer on the Czapek Yeast Extract Agar (11.44 µg/g CYA). The half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC50) was calculated for each EO. The results showed that the lowest IC50 value was obtained for the *Thymus capitatus* EO (245 µg/ml) followed by *Origanum onites* EO (398 µg/ml), the *Menthe Pouliot* EO (1175 µg/ml) and *Laurus nobilis* EO (5248 µg/ml). The OTA production by the *Aspergillus niger* strain was measured for each IC50. Variable degrees of inhibition were obtained: *Thymus capitatus* (59.83 %), *Origanum onites* (56.02 %), *Menthe Pouliot* (36.01 %) and *Laurus nobilis* (91.11 %). EO of *Laurus nobilis* (HE) was the most effective for the OTA synthesis.

Key words: *Aspergillus niger*, essential oils, ochratoxin A.

Supporting Fund: Valorization of Research Results (VRR) 2022 titled: BioProtect Grain.

Abstract N°: 13 (O13)

**CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES OF CAMEL MILK
YOGURT SUPPLEMENTED WITH CAROB SYRUP**

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For a long time, only fresh camel milk is traditionally used for its medicinal value and richness in bioactive, antimicrobial, and antioxidant substances. There is a growing demand to develop an efficient method of processing camel milk into functional dairy products. Processing camel milk into yogurt enriched with healthy foods such as carob syrup can provide nutritional benefits. The present study aimed to evaluate the impact of adding carob syrup on the chemical composition and antioxidant properties of camel milk yogurt. Protein, fat, carbohydrate, and dry matter contents were studied. Total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity (DPPH and ABTS assays) were evaluated. The addition of the carob syrup had significant effects ($p < 0,05$) on the chemical composition of the yogurt compared to the control sample by increasing the dry matter, fat, carbohydrate, and protein contents. Camel milk yogurt supplemented with carob syrup showed significantly ($p < 0,05$) higher values of total phenolic content, DPPH scavenging activity, and ABTS scavenging activity compared to control samples. In conclusion, carob syrup enriches the chemical composition and increases the antioxidant activity of camel milk yogurt, which could contribute to the diversification of camel milk dairy products.

Key words: camel milk, yogurt, carob syrup, antioxidant activity, chemical composition.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by the project: Valorization of camel milk by promoting a value chain based on a public-private partnership (PPP).

Abstract N°: 14 (O14)

Characterization of traditional Tunisian arid zone fermented goat milk, Rayeb, using *Enterococcus faecium* isolated from dromedary-fermented milk

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Rayeb is a traditional fresh Tunisian fermented milk beverage, previously made by nomads from the raw milk of their goats reared in arid zone. Unlike Rayeb from cow milk, characterized and industrialized using starter culture, that of goat remain artisanal with spontaneous fermentation, despite healthy benefits of this dairy product. *Enterococcus faecium*, a previously isolated and identified strain from dromedary spontaneous fermented milk (NCBI access number MN176627) was used as starter to product a safety goat Rayeb regarding its antibacterial activity. Physico- chemical analysis including pH, acidity, dry matter, proteins, minerals and organic acid composition were performed. In fact, *Enterococcus faecium*, allowed a drop in pH to 4.5 ± 0.01 , the isoelectric pH of goat milk after 12h fermentation at 37°C and a raise of acidity to $103 \pm 0.63^\circ\text{D}$. Which forms an important guarantee of product safeness. Goat milk rayeb with 119.8 ± 1.60 g/l dry matter can form a probiotic beverage containing $27.5 \text{ g/l} \pm 0.02$ proteins, 6.83 ± 0.19 g/l minerals and 29.21 g/l lactose.

Regarding diversity of organic acids detected before and after fermentation. *E. faecium* hosted mixed fermentation: homolactic and heterolactic characterized by their end-product respectively lactic acid (8.20 g/l) and acetic acid (1.76 g/l), where succinic acid (0.31 g/l) and propionic acids (0.67 g/l) seemed to be intermediate fermentation products.

Key words: goat milk, organic acids, *Enterococcus faecium*, Rayeb.

Abstract N°: 15 (O15)

Photosensitization effect of thyme essential oil for controlling plant pathogen *Botrytis cinerea* and *Alternaria alternata* in postharvest tomatoes

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Researching novel environmentally-friendly technologies, non-thermal and cost effective for microbial control of fresh and perishable produces, has gained considerable attention during last years. This work presented the first approach regarding application of essential oils mediated photosensitization for tomatoes decontamination. Thyme (*Thymus Capitatus*) essential oil was added at (100µg/mL) to petri dishes containing cultures of *Botrytis cinerea* and *Alternaria alternata*, they were simultaneously irradiated by UV-C (254nm) during 5, 10, 15 and 20 minutes. Results show that TEO based photosensitization exhibited the best antifungal activity. Indeed, the survival percent was reduced to 12% and 17% for *A.alternata* and *B.cinerea*, respectively. Fungal sporulation in PDA was gradually reduced by TEO photosensitization at at 100µg/mL thyme essential oil and 20 min UV-C irradiation time to 3% for *A. alternata* and to 2% for *B. cinerea* to 3% and 2%. In addition, TEO-based photosensitization significantly reduced the mean lesion diameter of *A. alternata* from 35 mm in untreated tomatoes to 15 mm in photosensitized ones after 7 days of storage period at 28°C. For *B. cinerea*, it was reduced from 39 mm to 18 mm in photosensitized treated samples.

Key words: Photosensitization; Thyme essential oil; UV-C irradiation; Tomatoes; Fungi.

Abstract N°: 16 (O16)

Effect of enzymatic hydrolysis on antioxidant activities of milk whey proteins from five different species

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Throughout the current study, the physicochemical composition of camel milk and whey was compared to that of different animal species milk: cow, goat, mare, and sheep. Furthermore, whey proteins were digested *in vitro* by the successive action of pepsin and pancreatin, simulating gastrointestinal digestion. Then, the effects of the enzymatic hydrolysis on the antioxidant activities of whey proteins from different animal species were studied. Electrophoresis was used to determine the composition and degradation of proteins (SDS-PAGE) and the ortho-phthalaldehyde (OPA) method was used to evaluate the peptide concentration and the degree of hydrolysis (DH). Except camel whey, which is distinguished by the absence of β -lactoglobulin and the presence of two distinct proteins (CWBP and PGRP), the results revealed that all five dairy species had identical proteins (α -lactalbumin, lactoferrin...). The antioxidant activities were evaluated using four assays, including 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and 2,20-azino- bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) radical-scavenging activities, β -carotene bleaching assay and ferrous ion chelating activity. The results showed that camel whey hydrolysates presented the highest DPPH radical scavenging activity (38.56%), whereas the cow whey hydrolysates presented 92.59% of ferrous ion chelating ability and the mare whey hydrolysates exhibited the highest β -carotene bleaching inhibition (80.80 %). Clearly, the enzymatic hydrolysis enhanced the antioxidant activity of whey proteins of different studied species. These results imply that milk whey proteins encrypted in their sequence antioxidant peptides and therefore hydrolysates are excellent natural preservatives.

Key words: Milk; Whey proteins; Enzymatic hydrolysis; Antioxidant activities; Bioactive peptides.

Abstract N°: 17 (O17)

Camel milk casein as a potent source of natural antioxidant peptides

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Besides providing essential amino acids, camel milk and in particular proteins can exhibit different biological activities. Camel milk differs markedly from cow milk in term of protein content, although the caseins content in camel milk is slightly higher. β -CN is the major protein in camel milk (65% of total CN), the α_{s1} -CN level (22%) is low and the proportion of κ -CN in camel milk is only 3% (vs. 10–12% in cow milk). Camel casein were successively hydrolyzed by pepsin and pancreatin using an *in vitro* protocol. The degradation of casein was characterized by electrophoresis and reversed-phase ultra-high performance liquid chromatography. Anti-oxidant activity was measured by the 2,2'-azino-bis-(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6- sulfonic acid) (ABTS) method. The Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) values of camel casein and its hydrolysate were $1.6 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{mol TE/mg protein}$ and $0.25 \mu\text{mol TE}/\mu\text{mol eq. NH}_2$, respectively. The enhancement of anti-radical activity after enzymatic hydrolysis is due to liberation of antioxidant peptides. Identification of peptides released by the action of the digestive enzymes was performed by tandem mass spectrometry, and six radical scavenging peptides liberated from β -CN were found by sequence alignment with known bioactive peptides. This explains that camel milk can be better preserved than the milks of other species

Key words: Camel Milk; Casein; Free radical scavenging activity; peptides; natural preservation.

Abstract N°: 18 (O18)

Camel skim milk fermented by newly isolated autochthonous probiotic *Lactococcus lactis*: Quality characteristics and anti-obesity properties

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Fermentation is among the methods used for milk biopreservation. Commercially available starter cultures are from bovine-based dairy industry being not competitive with endogenous microbiota of camel milk, which might not give a desirable final product. Hence, the objectives of this work were to elaborate fermented camel skim milk using *Lactococcus lactis*, a newly isolated probiotic strain from spontaneously fermented camel milk, and to determine the quality characteristics and the anti-obesity properties of this product. Camel skim milk fermentation by *Lactococcus lactis* was carried out at 37 °C until pH reached 4.4. Both unfermented and fermented camel skim milk were assessed for their physicochemical properties in terms of pH, acidity, viscosity, color, protein, lactose, ash and organic acids. In addition, the anti-obesity activity of camel milk before and after fermentation was evaluated *in vitro* using pancreatic lipase inhibitory test. The results showed that the fermentation of camel skim milk using the autochthonous strain *Lactococcus lactis* increased its acidity, viscosity as well as its color parameters (L^* , a^* and b^*). The chemical composition of fermented milk is comparable to that of unfermented camel milk except for the lactose content, which decreased after fermentation. The level of citric acid was not affected by the fermentation process, whereas the levels of succinic, lactic, formic, acetic and propionic acid increased after fermentation. Lactic acid was the major organic acid in fermented camel skim milk (8.12 g/L). Furthermore, the anti-obesity activity of fermented skim camel milk (8.18 %) was significantly higher than that of unfermented camel skim milk (53.81 %). Interestingly, simulated gastrointestinal digestion increased significantly the anti-obesity of fermented camel skim milk. Our findings suggest that fermented camel skim milk using the autochthonous strain *Lactococcus lactis* could be considered as a functional food.

Key words: Camel milk, fermentation, *Lactococcus lactis*, organic acids, anti-obesity.

Abstract N°: 19 (O19)

Anti-tumoral activity of *Allium roseum* compounds on Breast cancer cells MCF7 and MDA-MB231

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Global health data show that 66% of all cancer deaths worldwide occur in low- and middle-income countries. Breast cancer (BC) is the leading cause of cancer-related death in women worldwide, and presents with lower survival rates in Africa compared to Europe. This disparity could be due to important issues related to poor diagnostic services and limited access to treatment in Africa. These issues are major challenges in achieving health and well-being. However, it has been widely demonstrated that Mediterranean diet is enriched with plant-based nutrition, is associated with a lower risk of chronic diseases in the prevention of cancer. *Allium roseum* (AR) contains a range of beneficial plant compounds that are responsible for most of health benefits. The AR main phenolic compounds include flavonoids and phenolic acids that are essential for health benefit with its biological activities including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer properties. Current study indicates that AR extract exert a remarkable effect by modulating cancer cell death and proliferation on BC cell lines (MCF7 and MDA-MB231). Further studies on animal clinical trials are essentials for identifying the AR as a candidate for its beneficial effects on BC treatment and help to formulate its products as an integral part of the dietary and pharmacological intervention of patients with BC. The study contributes also to the discovery of pharmacological responses by identifying the affected genes and their functions.

Key words: *Allium roseum*, breast cancer cell, phenolics compounds

Abstract N°: 20 (O20)

How does dietary pomegranate peels incorporated in concentrate pellets affect lambs' meat quality and shelf life?

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These agriculture by-products of some noble fruits are rich in nutraceuticals and may be incorporated in feeds composition in order to cover animals supply and improve productivity and product quality. The present study was conducted to investigate the effects of integrating pomegranate peels at the level of 20% in concentrate pellets composition, on meat quality of D'Man lambs. The experiment involved 14 lambs of the breed D'Man aged 5 months with an average body weight of 24.3 kg. Lambs were divided into two groups (7 lambs each on each). Both groups received the same amount of oat hay, which increased from 800g/d to 900g/d and the same amount of concentrated pellets, which increased from 600g/d to 700g/d. The first batch (CC) received commercial concentrate feed, the second (GRD) received a concentrate feed containing 20% of the pomegranate. The animals were fattened for 98 days after which they were slaughtered and then the meat physiochemical properties were studied on *longissimus dorsi* muscle. The study of physio-chemical parameters of the meat from the different diets showed a significant difference between the groups in meat dry matter content (DM) ($P = 0.02$); in fact, the highest DM values were recorded for the CC group and the lowest values for the GRD group underlining a higher water retention when pomegranate peels are incorporated in lambs' diet. Besides, the meat the GRD group loses more water during cooking than the meat of the CC group, this may be related to the polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) melting during cooking. Moreover, the meat of both groups had similar values for color parameters a^* , b^* and L. The difference in lipid peroxidation indices was highly significant between groups ($P=0.0001$) with continued lower values for GRD meat during storage ($P=0.0001$). The resistance of GRD meat to lipid oxidation is associated to the higher content of polyphenols in pomegranate peels. Regarding meat fatty acid composition, the sum of PUFA and total conjugated linoleic fatty acid (CLA) were highly affected by the diet and the highest values were registered for the GRD group ($P= 0.078$; $P= 0.009$). The pomegranate peels incorporation in concentrate feed at the level of 20% has improved lamb meat micro and macro-chemical composition and limited its lipid oxidation during storage.

Key words: pomegranate peels, lambs' meat quality, lipid oxidation.

Abstract N°: 21 (O21)

Biological control methods against ochratoxin A-producing fungi isolated from grapes

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The main objective of the present work was to characterize the fungal flora of the Tunisian grape, and to propose biological control strategies against OTA-producing fungi present on grapes.

Obtained results showed that *A. carbonarius* is the dominant fungus representing nearly to 70% of the total fungal flora, it is the agent responsible for the production of OTA during the ripening period of grape. The evaluation of the antifungal and anti-ochratoxinogenic activities of *Salvia officinalis*, *Lavandula dentata* and *Laurus nobilis* essential oils (EOs), and their major constituent 1,8-cineole, was performed by two assays, contact assay and volatile assay. Statistical analyses of volatile assay showed that *L. nobilis* EO inhibited the growth rate much more than *L. dentata* and *S. officinalis* with a percentage equal to 47.82, 37.92 and 31.71%, respectively, and reduced the production of OTA with a percentage of 88.87%. While, on contact assay *L. nobilis* and *L. dentata* EOs exhibited a higher antifungal and anti-ochratoxinogenic activities than *S. officinalis*, with a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) about 0.3, 0.3 and 0.5%, respectively. The MIC of 1,8-cineole (0.5%) was approximately double to that of *L. nobilis* and *L. dentata* EOs. Hence, its powerful biological activities were assured by the synergism between the major component and the other existing ones. The evaluation of the antifungal and anti-ochratoxinogenic potential of *Aloe vera* gel revealed that this substance could inhibit the OTA production with a percentage up to 75.7% and reduce the mycelial growth of *A. carbonarius* (AC36) with an inhibition rate estimated at about 11.6%. The application of the suspensions of yeasts to the genus *Cryptococcus*, *Saccharomyces* and *Candida*, allowed a total inhibition of the growth and the production of OTA by *A. carbonarius* (AC36).

Key words: Grape, *A. carbonarius*, Ochratoxin A, Biological control.

International Seminar
Advances In Food Bio-Preservation
2-4 October 2022

SPECIAL SESSION: Multi-functional biomolecules from agro-industrial by-products: food bio-preservatives, antioxidants, *in vitro* and *in vivo* antidiabetic and anti-tumoral properties.

Abstract N°: 22 (O22)

Effects of antioxidant biomolecules extracted from agro-industrial byproducts on the prevention of diabetes and diabetic Retinopathy in Tunisian

Psammomys obesus model

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Food wastes are produced throughout all the food life cycle, 38% of them occurs during food processing. High-value components such as antioxidants could be recovered and be re-used as nutritionally and pharmacologically functional ingredients with large applications in functional foods supplementation, medicinal and pharmaceutical applications. Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a common complications associated with type 2 diabetes (T2D) leading to vision loss and irreversible blindness. In 2021, the International Diabetes Federation has estimated that 537 million people are currently living with diabetes worldwide. According to the same source, there will be 643 million adults with diabetes by 2030, and 783 million by 2045. Antioxidants recovered from agri-industrial waste could be tested by using animal models to mimic pathologies similar to those encountered in humans in order to investigate their cytotoxicity and/or protective effect. Tunisian *Psammomys obesus* (*P.ob*) is a high-fat diet-fed animal model of obesity and T2D recently explored and validated by our laboratory as a model of structure and function DR similar to that human. Many antioxidant biomolecules and agro-industrial extracts (oleuropein, Astaxanthin, hydroxytyrosol, Fucoxanthin brown algae, olive mill wastewater,) were investigated in our laboratory by using *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. Astaxanthin (AST) is a major marine carotenoid with powerful antioxidant and neuroprotective properties. The *in vitro* and *in vivo* protective effects of astaxanthin on the type-2 diabetic *P.ob* retinas was investigated. AST short-term administration did not rescue retinal ganglion cells and synaptic transmission in plexiform layers in diabetic gerbils. Retinal primary culture showed that the viability and the mitochondrial function increased significantly with astaxanthin addition on high glucose-induced stress conditions. Oleuropein is the main phenolic compound of olive leaves extracts. Oleuropein and aqueous extract of olive leaves attenuated glucose-induced cytotoxicity and protected retinal cells against the toxic effect of glucose by improving the viability of photoreceptors. Further experiments using Fucoxanthin (recovered from brown algae) and hydroxytyrosol (recovered from olive mill wastewater) are in progress and showed that these natural antioxidants could be used to prevent diabetes complications. *P.ob* is a useful model of HFD-induced obesity and diabetes to evaluate early retinal alterations and antioxidant neuroprotection mechanisms in DR. Besides *P.ob* retinal cells is a novel cell culture model that allows future investigations on the pathway by which dietary antioxidants may preserve retinal cells function from hyperglycemia.

Key words: antioxidant, oleuropein, Astaxanthin, hydroxytyrosol, Fucoxanthin brown algae, olive mill wastewater

Abstract N°: 23 (O23)

Anti-diabetic activity of camel milk; findings in pancreatic beta cells

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Controlling diabetes, a worldwide metabolic disease, by effective alternative treatments is currently a topic of great interest. Camel milk is believed to be a suitable hypoglycemic agent in experimental animals and patients with diabetes. This study was conducted to test the effect of raw, pasteurized and boiled camel milk on experimental induced diabetes. This effect will be tested on the pancreatic beta cells tissue using histopathological and morphometric essays. The effects of camel milk on diabetic animals were investigated by observing changes in the glycometabolic index (fasting blood glucose, IGTT test), the lipometabolic index (triglycerides, cholesterol), and total proteins and in the degree of injury of β -cells in the pancreatic islets. Raw camel milk consumption produced a significant decrease in fasting plasma glucose (from 9.77 ± 0.19 to 5.4 ± 0.13 mmol/L), cholesterol (from 6.94 ± 0.06 to 5.04 ± 0.8 mmol/L) and total proteins (from 75.31 ± 4.68 to 67.06 ± 3.32 g/L) in blood sample and an improvement on the animal clinical status (normal activity). The same result was showed in animals getting pasteurized camel milk (PCM): fasting blood glucose (from 9.83 ± 0.1 to 5.46 ± 0.22 mmol/L); cholesterol (from 7.25 ± 1.11 to 5.18 ± 0.97 mmol/L) total proteins (from 74.84 ± 5.45 to 67.06 ± 3.32 g/L). Treatment with raw or pasteurized camel milk also induces the renewal of pancreatic b-cells, which was confirmed by morphometric test. This test showed a significant difference in the ratio: pancreatic beta cells/total pancreatic cells ($p < 0.005$) when compared treated animals with the control. The curative effect of camel milk on experimental induced diabetic animals was approved in this study using raw or pasteurized camel milk as treatment. Pasteurized camel milk can be used as an alternative for better preservation of nutritional and therapeutic quality of this product.

Keywords: Camel milk, diabetes, beta- cells, morphometric test.

Abstract N°: 24 (O24)

Effects of olive mill wastewater compound on retinal function and astroglial glutamate metabolic networks in Diabetic Retinopathy *Psammomys obesus*

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Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is an endemic disease and is a major cause of impaired visual acuity. The aim of this study was to examine the effect of a purified compound from olive mill wastewater (OMWW) on retinal function and astroglial glutamate metabolic networks in DR *Psammomys obesus* model. Animals were divided into four groups (Control, Control with OMWW, Diabetic and Diabetic with OMWW). The Control group received a natural halophylic plant and Diabetic group was fed by a high fat diet (HFD) during 7 months. During the whole experimentation, body weight, glycemia, water and food intake were monitored. Retinal function and vascular changes were assessed using electroretinogram and optical Coherence Tomography, Fundus exam, fluorescein angiography; respectively. At different time points, Immunohistochemical studies was performed on paraformaldehyde fixed eyes. Retinal sections were prepared by cryostat and mounted on adhesive slides, then labeled with glial fibrillary acidic antibody (GFAP) an indicator of neuroglial cells reactivity; with Vesicular glutamate transporter1(VGlut-1), a major transporter responsible for loading glutamate into synaptic vesicles located in glutamatergic terminals of photoreceptors and bipolar cells. In addition, to Synaptophysin antibody (SVP38) staining, a presynaptic marker of both plexiform layers followed by confocal microscopy examination. Our key results at the stage of 3 and 5 months showed a glial reactivity manifested by an increase in GFAP in both diabetic and treated specimens compared to controls. In contrast, we note a low glutaminergic expression in treated diabetic group with a similar fluorescence pattern of VGlut-1 in diabetic retinas. Moreover, SVP38 throughout the plexiforms layers was less intense in diabetic group compared to controls due to a disruption of synaptic neurotransmission, a slight correction of SVP38 immunofluorescence was observed in treated diabetic group. These findings suggest that *P. obesus* is a useful model for testing biomolecules extracted from Tunisian medicinal plants in DR.

Key words: Diabetic Retinopathy, *Psammomys obesus*, Olive mill wastewater, retinal function, Immunohistochemistry.

Supporting Fund: This research is supported by the European Union funds under the framework of MOBIDOC-PROMESSE program coordinated by the National Agency for the Promotion of Scientific Research (ANPR) in partnership with Herbes de Tunisie Groupe AYACHI, N°343/2019.

Abstract N°: 25 (O25)

Effect of a biomolecule extracted from brown algae on molecular and cellular alterations in diabetic *Psammomys obesus* at the retinal and systemic level

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Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a diabetes complication that cause blindness worldwide. Risk factors for DR include a high blood glucose levels, hypertension and abnormal cholesterol level. This study aimed to investigate the direct effect of a biomolecule extracted from brown algae on highcaloric fed *Psammomys obesus*, a reference model of Diabetes type 2 and RD model. The kinetics of the pathology is done by *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies. *Psammomys obesus* were randomly divided into four groups: control, control positive (+) biomolecule, diabetes, diabetes+ biomolecule. Diabetes was induced by a high-fat diet (HFD) and the biomolecule was given by oral administration to the animals. Oxidative stress done by Malondialdehyde assay and Biochemical parameters (body weight, blood sugar, lipid profile, are determined over time. Histological studies of retinae are done at the end of the experiment. Retinal cells are cultivated under normal and ischemic conditions, in order to mimic the pathological state of diabetes. Viabilities of retinal cells are determined in different concentrations of molecules by trypan blue and using colorimetric method MTT. The different layers of the retina have been studied through immunocytochemical study by labeling of different retinal constituents such as photoreceptors, horizontal and glial cells. We used a fluorescence microscopy in order to check cell labeling and we used Image J software to process images. Type 2 diabetes, induced by high fat diet, cause hyperglycemia and led to progressive changes in the lipid profile of *Psammomys obesus*. Retinas were fixed and included in optimal cutting temperature (oct), for histological studies. Different concentrations of our biomolecule are tested in retinal cells primary cultures under normal condition (5 mM of glucose) and in hyperglycemic condition (25mM and 40 mM). The viability test showed an increase of cell viability even in ischemic condition. The immunocytochemical study came to confirm our results and showed that the biomolecule enhanced the expression of cones photoreceptors, the horizontal and glial cells, in the elevated glycemic cultures compared to the untreated culture and this proves the protective effect of the biomolecule extracted from marine brown algae. *Psammomys obesus* represents a reference model of diabetic and it would be a way to test the effects of the biomolecule in order to develop new therapeutic approaches.

Key words: Diabetic retinopathy; *Psammomys obesus*; High fat diet; Type II diabetes; brown algae extract; retinal function.

Supporting Fund: This thesis project is carried out within the framework of a joint Tunisian-South African project. It is supported by the laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules LR17ES03, Higher Institute of Biotechnology Sidi Thabet.

Abstract N°: 26 (O26)

Evaluation of anti-hyperlipidemic effect and antioxidant activities of carotenoids extracted from halophilic *Archaea* – Case study of hyperlipidemic mice

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The hyperlipidemia is a serious health problem that may increase the risk of many complications occurring, including cardiovascular disease. Carotenoids extracted from halophilic *Archaea* have potential health benefits. This study aims to evaluate the possible anti-hyperlipidemic effect and the antioxidative activities of the carotenoids extracted from the halophilic *Archaea* in male mice fed with a high-fat diet (HFD). Seventy male albino mice were randomly divided into seven experimental groups of ten each, receiving different diets during 5 weeks. Food intakes of the animals were recorded daily, and their body weights were monitored twice a week throughout the experiment. At the end of the experimental period, the mice were sacrificed, the blood samples were collected and the livers, kidneys and hearts were removed and weighted. The plasma lipid profile and the serum biochemical indices were determined. The thiobarbituric acid reactive substances level, the antioxidant enzyme activities in liver, kidney and heart and the histological examination were estimated. The carotenoids administration improved dose-dependent lipid profile, as well as the liver and renal dysfunction indices in hyperlipidemic mice. Moreover, the halophilic carotenoids also restored the antioxidant status in liver, kidney and heart by lowering the lipid peroxidation and enhancing the antioxidant enzymes (catalase, glutathione peroxidase and superoxide dismutase) under HFD-induced oxidative stress. Furthermore, the histological study proved that the carotenoids administration prevents hepatic steatosis, glomerular hyperfiltration risk, and cardiac muscle hypertrophy. Accordingly, the carotenoids are a promising novel medicinal ingredient for possible use in the hyperlipidemic treatment and its related complications.

Key words: Carotenoids, high-fat diet, Antioxidant activities, Anti-hyperlipidemia.

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Abstract N°: 27 (E -Poster 1)

***Allium Sativum* and *Artemisia Campestris* extracts against cattle Feed Mold infestation**

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Feedstuffs can be seriously contaminated by mycotoxigenic fungi that cause serious economic and health problems for animals and humans. Phytoextracts has been documented as an alternative tool against fungal feed contamination. The aim of this study is to investigate the *Allium Sativum* and *Artemisia Campestris* extracts antifungal activities, against *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* species and to evaluate the richness of these extracts in biomolecules by LCMS. Target mycotoxigenic fungi species has been isolated from cattle feed samples and they are identified by biomolecular sequencing as *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium polonicum*, mainly associated with feed biodeterioration during storage. Phyto-extracts were obtained by maceration using methanol, ethyl acetate and hexane. Extracts dry residues has been prepared as 40 to 1,25 mg/ml DMSO solutions and used to evaluate their antifungal activities. The phytochemical screening showed that studied herbal extracts are riche by phenolic acid, flavonoid, water-soluble vitamins and phytosterols. Some extracts showed a co-presence of more than 8 biomolecules with a concentration ranging from 47.797 to 0.822 mg/kg, particularly for methanolic extracts, Although the lowest concentrations were recorded for hexanoic extracts. *Allium Sativum* extract has showed very important antifungal proprieties, especially for methanolic extract that shoe 96,5% inhibition percentage against *Aspergillus flavus*. The same for ethyl acetate extract that revealed an important activity against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium polonicum*. Extracts of the *Artemisia Campestris* have recorded also significant antifungal activities against tested species, among them, A. flavus recorded high susceptibility with relative inhibition percentage ranging from 92.39±3,8% to 39.8±4,2%, for *penicillium*, inhibition rates are recorded between 65.4±5,1% and 11.42 ±5,7% for the same extracts.

Keywords: Feed, Fungi, Garlic, Artemisa, extract, antifungal, LCMS.

Abstract N°: 28 (E -Poster 2)

Valorization and competitiveness improvement through emerging technologies applied to food by-products within the circular economy framework (VallCET)

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The Mediterranean Agri-food value chain, which represents a complex systems involving several local actors, such as farmers, small-scale food manufacturers, and local distributors among others, is challenged by the dual objective of (i) enhancing competitiveness, which is currently challenged by non-optimized organizational model, long supply chain and imported low price products of global markets, and (ii) improving sustainability of the productions and increase safety and quality of food products. In this line, VallCET project “Valorise foods and Improve Competitiveness through Emerging Technologies applied to food by-products within the circular economy framework” (2021-2023) is funded through the PRIMA (Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area) by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR, Tunisia). It involves a consortium of 5 academic partners and 4 SME spanning Spain, Italy, Portugal, France, and Tunisia. VallCET aims at developing novel strategies for the valorisation of wastes and by-products from post-farming processes of Mediterranean agri-food systems and the design of eco-friendly processes to recover high-added value bioactives to be reintroduced in the agri-food chain as food ingredients/additives within the circular economy framework. The functional ingredients/additives with high nutritional value, antioxidant capacity and antimicrobial activity can contribute to reduce post-farming food losses during transportation and storage, to improve the nutritional and sensory quality and to extend the shelf-life of Mediterranean food products such as fruits, bakery, wine and dairy products.

Supporting Fund: This research is funded by the VallCET project (2021-2023) which is funded through the PRIMA (Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area) by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR, Tunisia).

Key words: Date byproducts, functional additives, biopreservation, food shelf life, circular economy

Abstract N°: 29 (E -Poster 3)

Antioxidant activity of Garlic and coriander powder and their use as bio-preservatives in a salted dried meat

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Herbals such as garlic and coriander have strong antimicrobial and antioxidant properties due to their rich composition in bioactive compounds, especially phenolic compounds. They are often used in medicinal science and culinary preparations. Nowadays, these plants are incorporated in food products as bio-preservatives providing a powerful alternative for the food industry in response to consumer demand. The aim of this work was, to study the antioxidant activity of garlic and coriander powder and to determine their optimal concentration to improve the oxidative stability and the sensorial properties of a traditional salted meat (kaddid). Garlic cloves were peeled, cut and dried in an oven for 11 hours at 60°C. The coriander seeds were washed and sun dried for 3 days. The garlic and coriander were then ground to a fine powder. The results of antioxidant activity obtained by DPPH method showed a higher percentage of inhibition for garlic powder (IC₅₀=64%) when compared to coriander powder (IC₅₀ = 4.15%). This result was confirmed by the polyphenol content which was significantly higher for the garlic powder. The antimicrobial activity determined by disc diffusion method revealed a high inhibition diameter zone (22.3mm) for the garlic powder against *Salmonella arizonae*. An optimal concentration of garlic and coriander powder was determined by an experimental design. The level of incorporation was established on the basis of the results of preliminary trials conducted using different concentrations of each spice and on the basis of sensory attributes and oxidative stability. The optimal spices concentrations of garlic and coriander powder were 4% (W/W) and 6% (W/W), respectively.

Key words: garlic powder; coriander powder, antioxidant activity, bio-preservation, kaddid.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

Abstract N°: 30 (E -Poster 4)

Optimization of hesperidin extraction from orange byproduct and screening of the antibacterial activity

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The total phenol and flavonoid content, hesperidin content and antioxidant activity of orange byproducts were determined for different operating conditions using three extraction processes: conventional solvent extraction, CSE (ethanol (0-100%), m/v: 5g:50ml, 30 min, 70°C and mechanical stirring in dark), ultrasound assisted extraction, UAE (ethanol (0,40,80%), m/v: 5g:50ml, 30 min, temperature (25; 47,5; 70°C) and ultrasonic power (0, 200, 400W), and accelerated solvent extraction, ASE (ethanol (30,60,90%), m/v: 5g:50ml, 30 min, temperature (40, 70, 100, 130°C). The highest amounts of hesperidin and the strongest antioxidant activities were obtained with ethanol 80%, 70°C for CSE; ethanol 80%, 70°C, 200 W for UAE; and ethanol 60%, 100°C, and 100 bar for ASE. The antibacterial activity, the MBC and MIC of the extracts were determined. The highest amounts of hesperidin and the strongest antioxidant activities were obtained with ethanol 80%, 70°C for CSE; ethanol 80%, 70°C, 200 W for UAE; and ethanol 60%, 100°C, and 100 bar for ASE. Orange byproduct extracted by ASE present the highest hesperidin content (1.37± 0.06 g/100g DM) and antioxidant activity (14.94±0.029 mg TE/g DM). For the antibacterial result for the eight reference strains tested, the inhibition zone was between 8 and 14 mm and MIC and MBC were between 6 and 100 mg/ml.

Key words: orange byproducts, hesperidin, antioxidant activity, extraction methods, optimization.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by MOBIDOC scheme, project reference N°435, Session 2019

Abstract N°: 31 (E -Poster 5)

***Limosilactobacillus fermentum* from fermented milk: phylogenetic analyses and whole genome analysis**

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This work aims to study *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* strains named also *Lactobacillus fermentum* originally isolated from spontaneously fermented milk, compare its genome with the genomes of other *L. fermentum* strains, and provide an overview of its potential and functional applications in food products. *L. fermentum* was isolated from goat and cow fermented milk and identified using Ribosomal Multilocus Sequence Typing and Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI). Thirty publicly available genomes of *L. fermentum* from the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) were used for comparison and phylogeny analysis. Based on phylogenetic analysis and whole genome comparison isolated strains were similar to *Lactobacillus fermentum* 3872 and ACA-DC 179. These two strains were previously described as promising probiotic bacteria mainly for their antimicrobial activity, cholesterol reduction, immunomodulatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant activities, as well as maintenance of gut barrier integrity properties with safety criteria concerning hemolytic activity and antibiotic resistance. In food production, fermentation using *L. fermentum* leads to obtaining products with high sensory quality, texture, stability, and nutritional properties. Further applications in food matrixes will be performed to confirm technological and probiotic properties of this *Lactobacillus fermentum* isolate.

Key words: *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*- spontaneous fermentation of goat and cow milk, whole genome analysis.

Supporting Fund: This work was funded within the EU PRIMA project-2018 "Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods

Abstract N°: 32 (E -Poster 6)

Citrus peel extract as promising natural bio-preservative and food additive

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This study aimed to evaluate lemon citrus peel powder and extract as a potential food additive and food bio-preservative. Ethanoic extract (ethanol: 80%, v/v; 30 min, 40°C, rotational speed of 200 rpm) was prepared, concentrated and freeze dried. Antioxidant activity, total phenolic, and total flavonoid contents were measured. LC ESI MS and gas chromatography was used to determine phenolic and volatiles profiles. The antimicrobial activity of citrus lemon peel extract was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Listeria monocytogenes*. Results show that total phenolic and flavonoids contents were 2.32 g GAE/100g and 1.7 g QE/100g respectively. Antioxidant activity was 1.02 g TE/100g. A total of 11 volatiles compounds were detected in citrus peel powder namely α -phellandrene, trans- β -ocimene, β -pinene, 6-methyl-5-hepten-2-one, β -myrcene, β -cymene, limonene, γ -terpinene, 1-Hexen-3-yne, 2,5,5-trimethyl, geraniol, and sabinene. Limonene was the major volatile compound (68.69 %). The phenolic profile showed the presence of 30 compounds: quinic acid was the predominant compound ($\sim 3.3 \pm 0.1$ mg/g dry extract). Ethanoic extract of lemon citrus peel exhibited an antimicrobial activity with an inhibition zone varying from 10 to 12 mm and a minimum inhibitory concentration ranging from 12 to 25 mg/ml. *S. aureus* was the most sensitive strain to lemon citrus extract. Further investigations are required to evaluate the food bio-preservative effect of lemon citrus peel extract.

Supporting Fund: This work was funded within the EU PRIMA project-2018 "Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods"

Key words: Lemon Citrus peel- phenolic compounds- Volatiles compounds- antimicrobial activity.

Abstract N°: 34 (E -Poster 8)

Assessment of antioxidant properties of *Salicornia arabica* methanolic and decocted extracts

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The present study aimed to investigate the bioactive phenolic content of *Salicornia arabica* (*Chenopodiaceae* family) and to assessment of their antioxidant potential by *in vitro* assays using three different methods. The extraction procedure of phenolic compounds from powdered *S. arabica* aerial parts was carried out in maceration and decoction methods using methanol 80% (v/v) and distilled water as solvents, respectively. The residual aqueous fraction has been also recovered. Colorimetric methods using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and aluminum chloride were carried out to estimate total polyphenols, and flavonoids content of extracts. 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), anti-radical and antioxidant activity (ABTS) and metal ions (ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP)) were used to determine *in vitro* antioxidant activity. The main results of this study have shown that the extracts obtained have an interesting anti-radical and antioxidant activity (ABTS), compared to the DPPH radicals and FRAP. The strongest activity against radical scavenging of DPPH, ABTS and FRAP was found in the methanolic extract which contains highest amounts of total polyphenols (7.79 ± 0.02 g GAE/100g extract) and flavonoids (4.20 ± 0.01 mg QE/g), whereas the decocted extract presented the lowest antioxidant activity. The obtained results suggest that *S. arabica* powder can be used as source of antioxidants and beneficial for human health. These extracts can also be used as food additives and evaluate their effect on food biopreservation.

Key words: phenolics compound, *Salicornia arabica*, Methanolic and decocted extract, phytochemical screening, antioxidant activity.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by MOBIDOC scheme, project reference N°417, Session 2019.

Abstract N°: 35 (E -Poster 9)

Pyrolysis of lemon peel waste in a fixed-bed reactor: Characterization of innovative pyrolytic products with antioxidant and antibacterial activities

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In order to produce biochar, bio-oil, and gas, lemon peel waste (LPW) was pyrolyzed in a laboratory scale fixed bed reactor at final temperatures of 300°C, 400°C, and 500°C and a gradual heating rate of 10°C/min. By using GC-MS and FTIR spectroscopy, the chemical evaluation of bio-oil reveals its abundance in bioactive chemicals as squalene, D-limonene, β -Sitosterol, and phenol. The recovered bio-char is a promising applicant for the manufacturing of carbon materials and for solid fuel applications. Biochar and bio-oil showed bactericidal activity against *Bacillus cereus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The produced gas has a maximum calorific value around 12 MJ/N.m³ with a composition up to 75.87 vol.% of CO, 5.25 vol.% of CH₄, 1.48 vol.% of CnHm. Pyrolytic products of LPW show large potential applications in agriculture and the agri-food industries and allow sustainable biomass-waste management with promising economic benefits. The generated gas can contain up to 75.87 % of CO, 5.25 % of CH₄, and 1.48 of % CnHm, with a maximum calorific value of 12 MJ/N.m³. Pyrolytic products from LPW have a wide range of possible uses in the agri-food and agricultural sectors and enable the management of biomass waste in a way that is both environmentally friendly and economically advantageous.

Keywords: lemon peel waste; pyrolysis; fixed bed reactor; biofuels; biochar.

Abstract N°: 36 (E -Poster 10)

Development of functional cream dessert based on lentisk dough

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This study is performed in order to integrate the lentisk fruit in the agri-food sector by using its dough in the making of a « cream dessert » because of its nutritional properties and in order to satisfy the consumer. Analysis of this raw material indicates its abundance in fat (60.82 ± 7.46 g/100 MS) and minerals (1.73 ± 0.01 g/100 MS). It also contains high levels of phenolic compounds such as total polyphenols (3.55 ± 2.4 mg AG/g MS). Added to this, it has a good microbiological quality. However, the ethnobotanical study shows the deficiency of the incorporation of this fruit in commercial food products.

The optimization of the cream recipe was performed by using the response surface method and a centred compound design reduced to two factors (amount of lentisk and sugar) and to 3 levels. The sensory evaluation of the product showed the appreciation of the naive consumer of the lentisk cream. The follow-up of the new product during its refrigerated storage (6° C) for 21 days shows that this fruit has a preservative role.

Key words: oilseed plant, lentisk, dessert cream, experience plan, sensory analysis optimization.

Abstract N°: 37 (E -Poster 11)

Quality attributes and antioxidants of yogurt supplemented with lemon peel powder

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Stirred yogurt was supplemented with lemon peel powder (0-1%) as functional ingredients. The physico-chemical, antioxidant, textural, and sensory, properties of stirred yogurt were investigated. Supplementation of stirred yoghurt with 1% of lemon peel powder allows the improvement of its antioxidant and textural properties without any significant deterioration of its sensorial properties ($p>0.05$). The supplemented stirred yogurt presented higher titratable acidity and lower pH values during cold storage than those of unfortified yogurts. Total phenols contents and radical scavenging activities of fortified stirred yogurts increased with increasing lemon peel powder content (+32% for total phenols and +34% for radical scavenging activity for 1% fortified yogurt) and decreased with storage time (-31% for total phenols and -20% for radical scavenging activity for 1% fortified yogurts after 21 days of cold storage).

Keywords: yogurt, lemon peel, antioxidants, texture, sensory characteristics.

Abstract N°: 38 (E -Poster 12)

Effect of olive leaves powder supplementation on quality attributes and antioxidants of fresh milk cheese

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Three formulations of fresh cheese made from cow milk and supplemented with olive leaves powder (0.5, 1, 1.5%) were prepared and compared to not supplemented fresh cheese. The incorporation of the olive leaves powder did not affect the physico-chemical characteristics of cheese, except for colorimetric parameters, fat and ash contents. However, it positively affects total phenols content and radical scavenging activity. The incorporation of olive leaves powder at different levels (0.5, 1 and 1.5%) in fresh cheeses lead to the increase of total phenols content (54.17%, 59.26%, and 64.52%; compared to control cheese). The same trend was found for the radical scavenging activity. Sensory analysis has shown that some sensory descriptors have been significantly changed such as color, odor, taste and after taste. The fresh cheese supplemented with 0.5% of olive leaves powder is the most appreciated product by the panelists, suggesting that these products could help to promote public health as functional foods.

Keywords: olive leaves, antioxidants, fresh cheese, sensory properties, chemical properties.

Abstract N°: 39 (E -Poster 13)

Nutritional composition and antioxidant activity of three selected ingredients (*Spirulina plantesis*, Fishmeal and wheat flour) for fish feed formulation

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This study was carried out to investigate the nutritional composition and to assess the bioactivity of *Spirulina plantesis*, fish meal and flour wheat obtained from Aquaculture Company «Jinan life», Agri Business Company -Sidi Daoud and the local market respectively. The proximate composition and total phenolic content were determined using standard methods. The antioxidant activity was determined by the radical scavenging activity of the methanol extract of samples against DPPH (Sigma Aldrich) by UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at 517 nm. *Spirulina plantesis* exhibited the highest crude protein content (63.66% of fresh weight) while the lowest was observed in wheat flour (12.96% of fresh weight). Arginine and leucine were the predominant essential amino acids (EAA) accounting for 1.39-9.04% and 4.71-5.43%, respectively for all samples. The crude fat content ranged from 0.98% (*Spirulina plantesis*) to 27.14% (wheat flour). The most abundant lipid acids were saturated fatty acids in *S. plantesis* and fishmeal samples, and polyunsaturated fatty acids and omega-6 in the wheat flour. Total phenols were for 72.03±2.36, 74.95±3.56 and 76.81±2.48 mg EAG/100 g wheat flour, fishmeal, *Spirulina plantesis* extracts respectively. Total flavonoids were 92.72±4.59, 585.42±6.89 and 409.23±9.54 mg EQ/100 g for wheat flour, fishmeal, *Spirulina plantesis* extracts respectively. Radical scavenging activity of the extract against DPPH were 54.26±0.31, 30.93±0.32 and 15.80±0.15 mg ET/100 g for wheat flour, fishmeal, *Spirulina plantesis* extracts respectively. Wheat flour, fishmeal, *Spirulina plantesis* could be used as animal feed ingredients having besides of their nutritional value, antioxidants properties.

Key words: *Spirulina plantesis*, Fishmeal, Wheat flour, Nutritional, Antioxidant.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by MOBIDOC scheme, project reference N°673, Session 2019.

Abstract N°: 40 (E -Poster 14)

Growth inhibition of common foodborne pathogens in the presence of Tunisian culinary spices extracts

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The objective of this study was to investigate the inhibitory effect of natural antibacterial Mint (*Mentha spicata*) and Paprika (*Capsicum annum*) ethanolic extracts against the growth of three pathogenic bacteria under a temperature of 37°C using predictive modeling. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) and bacterial inhibition percentage against three pathogens; *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* were examined at different concentrations of the extracts. To describe the growth/survival of organisms in the presence of the extracts, the suitability of three kinetic models, Huang, modified Gompertz and logistic were explored. The parameters and the performance of these predictive primary models were assessed using the least squares methodology. The root minimum square errors (RMSE) and correlation coefficients (R^2) were determined using R software packages. The results of the present study indicated that both extracts were highly effective at low concentrations against the gram-positive bacteria. The minimum inhibitory concentrations presented a range of 1.65 to 12.5 mg /ml. Mint extract demonstrated the highest inhibition levels against *Listeria monocytogenes* ranged from 37.4% to 87.6% and Paprika extract exhibited the higher inhibition against *Micrococcus luteus* ranged from 45.4-98.2%, respectively. The addition of paprika and mint extracts resulted a bacterial reduction of 23% to 62% and % 35 to 79%, respectively, in the stationary level growths as compared to the control. First-order modeling mostly provided a good fitting to the experimental data and indicated a significant difference in growth rate depending on the concentration of each extract. Upon even lower concentrations, the lag phase was prolonged, and both the maximum specific growth rate and final population densities were reduced.

This work suggests that these extracts have the potential of imparting microbiological safety to food products. However, further developments and optimization are required.

Key words: Natural extract, Foodborne pathogens, Growth inhibition, Mathematical modelling.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by the project: -PRIMA project Artisanefood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods 2019-2022

Abstract N°: 41 (E -Poster 15)

Stability of sardine flesh powder and fishmeal byproducts during storage

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Drying is the most common methods used since antiquity for food preserving. This process lowers food humidity in order to improve its stability in storage. Therefore sardine, perishable and a good nutritive fish was completely transformed according to the process described by (Tarhouni et al, 2018).

In this work, obtained products (flesh powders and fishmeal byproducts) were conditioned differently (irradiation at 5Kgy, vacuum packaging, addition of 0.5% of a natural antioxidant (orange peel powder) and addition of 5% of NaCl). The stability of these products during for 12 months at room temperature was studied. The following parameters are evaluated (i) nutritional value (proteins, total lipids, fatty acid composition), (ii) physical parameters (color, pH, water activity), (iii) quality indicators (total volatile nitrogen ABVT-N, lipid oxidation TBARS, biogenic amines) and (iiii) quality microbiological.

According to this study, we have noticed that, with the exception of the fat oxidation and the variation in the fatty acid content recorded for byproducts fishmeal, both flesh powder and byproducts fishmeal are relatively stable in terms of chemical composition and microbiological quality. Irradiation resulted in a better preservation of the microbiological quality. Vacuum packaging guaranteed better physicochemical, functional and nutritional proprieties stability of the products and inhibited the oxidation of lipids. With good nutritional potential and good stability, the flesh powder can be an effective ingredient to formulate other products intended for human consumption. Moreover, byproducts fishmeal constitutes a raw material for pellets (aquaculture feed) production or other formulations for animal feed.

Key words: sardine, flesh powder, byproducts fishmeal, stability, formulation

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by the Italy-Tunisia cross-border cooperation program and is performed in the BIOVecQ PS1.3_08 project (Biotechnologie Marine Vecteur d'Innovation & Qualité), 2007-2013.

Abstract N°: 42 (E -Poster 16)

Olive Mill Wastewater extract: a rich source for phenols and antioxidant recovery with potent applications in food bio-preservation and nutraceuticals

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The aim of this work was to determine total phenols, radical scavenging activity and cytotoxicity of olive mill wastewater extract. Total phenols and total flavonoids content were determined by spectrophotometric methods. Antioxidant activity was determined by the radical scavenging activity of the extract against DPPH (Sigma Aldrich) by UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at 517 nm. Cytotoxicity was assessed by trypan blue exclusion dye and MTT assay on primary retinal cells of the Gerbil *Psammomys Obesus*. Total phenols and total flavonoids were 230.00 ±7.58 mg EAG/L and 417.88±16.37 mg EQ/L respectively. Radical scavenging activity of the extract against DPPH is about 44.71±0.54 mg ET/L with an inhibition percentage of 77.00±0.87 %. This activity is related to the main phenolic compounds of the extract. The evaluation of the extract's cytotoxicity is in progress

Olive mill wastewater extract shows a valuable antioxidant content and antioxidant activity with potent application as food bio-preservative in food formulation or as nutraceuticals. Further explorations will be performed to investigate olive mill wastewater extract properties and purify main phenolic compounds as well as their characterization.

Key-words: Olive mill wastewater extract, phenols, cytotoxicity

Supporting Fund: This research is supported by the European Union funds under the framework of MOBIDOC-PROMESSE program coordinated by the National Agency for the Promotion of Scientific Research (ANPR) in partnership with Herbes de Tunisie Groupe AYACHI, N°343/2019.

Abstract N°: 43 (E -Poster 17)

Antibacterial and antioxidant properties of humic substances derived from different sources: review

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Humic substances (HS), which are organic matter distributed in terrestrial soil, natural water, and sediments resulting from the decay of vegetable and natural residues, have been applied in different fields, such as agriculture or medicine as a sustainable alternative to the use of industrial synthetic products for the control of human or plants diseases. Several studies investigated the antimicrobial and the antioxidant capacity of HS derived from different sources. It was reported that HS has a significant antibacterial activity against *Salmonella typhi*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*. For antioxidant activity, HS exhibited significant free radical scavenging, especially against DPPH and superoxide anions; and a moderate effect on hydroxyl and hydrogen peroxide scavenging. The antioxidant effect of humic substances is probably related to the content of electron-donating phenolic groups and the presence of acid groups. However, it was reported that the antioxidant activity of HS extracts from green composts showed a direct correlation with their total phenolic content. We recently investigated the effect of HS on meat quality of broiler chickens and our results showed that this molecule did not affect the colorimetric parameters of the breast meat compared to the control group during a 24h storage period and improves sensory attributes of cooked breast meat ($P < 0.05$).

Based on the studies mentioned above, that are proven the antioxidant and the antimicrobial properties of HS, explorations will be performed to investigate the potent application of these substances as food bio-preservative in food formulation.

Key words: Humic substances, Antibacterial properties, antioxidant properties.

Supporting Fund: This research is supported by the European Union funds under the framework of MOBIDOC-PROMESSE program coordinated by the National Agency for the Promotion of Scientific Research (ANPR) in partnership with Poulina Group Holding, N211 (2018).

Abstract N°: 44 (E -Poster 18)

Effect of Thermal Treatments on the Fatty Acids Composition, Antioxidant and Anti-inflammatory Properties of Camel Milk

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The present research was conducted to study heat treatment effect on camel milk fatty acid composition and biological activities.

Fresh camel milk was obtained from a camel herd of the Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, Arid Lands Institute (Medenine, Tunisia). Milk samples were heated at 63°C for 30 minutes, 90°C for 3 minutes, and 100°C for 3 minutes. After heating, the milk fat was extracted by centrifugation of camel milk and fatty acids composition of all fat samples were quantified and identified using FAME 37 internal standards. The antioxidant activity of camel milk was evaluated by different assays, including free radical-scavenging activity (DPPH and ABTS) and ferric-reducing power assay (FRAP). The anti-inflammatory activity was determined against the enzyme 5-Lipo-oxygenase.

In fact, fifty percent of the total fatty acid composition was presented by saturated fatty acids (SFA). Heat treatment didn't show any significant effect on SFA amount (g/100 g) while the monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) were significantly higher in the unheated: 44.07 ± 3.65 g/100 g milk compared to treated milk (40.46 ± 4.9 g/100 g (63°C); 38.78 ± 2.71 g/100 g (90°C) and 37.46 ± 2.15 g/100 g (100°C). Among PUFAs, linoleic acid (LA) and alpha-linoleic acid (ALA) are respectively the major n-6 PUFA and n-3 PUFA in milk. There is no significant difference between omega 3 and omega 6 and the n-6/ n-3 ratio between raw, pasteurized, and boiled milk. Although, the higher ratio of n-3 was in unheated and low pasteurized camel milk which is well known for greater health benefits.

Heat treatment didn't show any significant effect on antioxidant activities. While a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) was shown after boiling the milk in the anti-inflammatory activity. Therefore, low pasteurization could be the greatest heating process to ensure the microbiological safety and the stability of the micronutrients in milk.

Key words: Camel milk; Heat treatment; Fatty acids; Biological activities.

Abstract N°: 45 (E -Poster 19)

Effect of Gamma Radiation and Refrigeration on the Bioactivities and Bioactive content of Strawberries

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The aim of this work was to study the effects of ionizing radiation (gamma radiation) in combination with storage (14 days) at 4°C on the antimicrobial and antidiabetic activities, cytotoxicity, and bioactive content of fresh strawberries. The irradiation experiments were carried out at room temperature in a Co-60 experimental equipment at 1, 2 and 3 kGy. Total Phenolic content (TP) was quantified by Folin-Ciocalteu method and Flavonoids content by a spectrophotometric method. The antioxidant activity was measured by DPPH radical scavenging activity and Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP). Antimicrobial activity was assessed against Gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichiacoli* (ATCC 8739), *Salmonella enterica* Typhimurium (ATCC 14028) and *Pseudomonasfluorescens*; and Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 6538), *Bacillus cereus* (SSIC 1/1), and *Listeria monocytogenes* (ATCC 19111) and the yeast *Candida albicans* (ATCC 10231). The antidiabetic activity of strawberry extracts was evaluated by assays, namely α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activity. Concerning cytotoxicity of fruit extracts, it was assessed by WST-1 assay for Cell Proliferation and Viability using human lung carcinoma epithelial cells (A549, ATCC® CCL-185 TM) and human embryonic kidney epithelial cells (293T, ATCC® CRL-3616™). To evaluate the shelf-life extension of strawberries, all the samples were analyzed immediately after irradiation (T0), after 7 (T7) and after 14 days of storage (T14) at 4 °C. Non-irradiated samples (0 kGy) were used as control and followed all the experiments. The results indicated that irradiated strawberries at 2 kGy and refrigerated presented significantly higher antioxidant activity and significantly increased inhibitory activity of α -glucosidase and α -amylase compared with non-treated strawberries. Concerning cytotoxicity assay, non-tumor 293T cells were more sensitive to strawberry extracts than A549 tumor cells but ionizing radiation had no impact on the viability of both cell lines. The gamma radiation treatment of strawberries points out to preserve the microbiostatic activity of ethanolic extracts against some of the tested microorganisms. These results pointed out that gamma radiation at 2 kGy can be used as safe environmentally friendly post-harvest treatments of strawberries to preserve their bioactivities and bioactive content.

Key words: Irradiated strawberries, Antimicrobial activity, Antidiabetic activities, Cytotoxicity, Bioactive content.

Supporting Fund: This work was developed within the Portuguese - Tunisian Bilateral Research Project funded by Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) and Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR, Tunisia) "Conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing: effects on product quality, safety, antioxidants and anti-diabetic potential, 2019-2021". The work was also developed in the scope of the Coordinated Research Project D61024 "Development of New Applications of Machine Generated Food Irradiation Technologies" financed by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA).

Abstract N°: 46 (E -Poster 20)

**Hypoglycemic effects of antioxidant plant extracts in *Psammomys obesus* rat,
In vivo and *in vitro* investigations**

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While there is no definitive cure for Diabetes to date, many different approaches have been used to treat this multifactorial disease, including diet control, sport, behavior therapy and medications. Among these therapies, controlling the dietary nutritional and changing in eating behavior for healthy life are of great interest. In addition, the use of natural compound especially, antioxidant agent, as Nutraceutical, is a very interesting and cheap costing way and constitutes a first line of therapy. The present study aims to investigate the *in vivo* and *in vitro* hypoglycemic and antioxidant effects of several plants extracts containing carotenoids, flavonoids and/or polyphenol, on the brain and the retinae of *Psammomys obesus* (*P. obesus*), a semi-desert rodent, extensively used as an animal model for nutritionally induced diabetes and metabolic syndromes. In previous studies, we demonstrated that *P. obesus*, when submitted to a high caloric diet during 12 weeks, develops type 2 diabetes, leading to diabetic retinopathy with similar structural and functional vision alterations to that observed in humans. In this brief presentation, we will show how diabetes affects the cerebral and retinal function with a focus on investigations done in our own laboratory. Oral administration of antioxidants extract, are highly useful in slowing down or restraint the development of Type 2 diabetes, obesity and dyslipidemia. These effects may involve the improvement of lipid metabolism, hepatic marker and renal marker. Additionally, *in vitro* investigations, revealed, that antioxidant extract treatment improves nerve cell survival, in response to an ischemic condition caused by a high concentration of glucose in the culture medium. Hence, the present study provides useful information and supports the traditional use of antioxidant plants extracts in the prevention and self-treatment of several ailments.

Key words: Diabetes, *Psammomys obesus*, antioxidant, hypoglycemic, *in vitro* assay

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by the project: PAQ- Collabora (PAR&I-Tk), period 2020-2022.

Abstract N°: 47 (E -Poster 21)

Isolation, characterization and identification of lactic acid bacteria from spontaneously fermented camel milk

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There is a growing need for new promising lactic acid bacteria (LAB) strains since the dairy industry is continuously asking for diversifying the available products. The aims of this study were to isolate, characterize and identify LAB from spontaneously fermented camel milk. Autochthonous LAB strains were selected from Tunisian spontaneously fermented camel milk based on their capacity to coagulate milk and they were identified using 16S rDNA gene sequencing. The technological and probiotic potential of these strains in terms of proteolytic, acidifying and lipolytic activities, exopolysaccharide production, antibacterial potential, hemolytic activity, antibiotic susceptibility, autoaggregation, co-aggregation, hydrophobicity and tolerance to simulated gastrointestinal conditions, were determined. Gene sequencing of LAB strains revealed four strains as *Enterococcus faecalis*, one strain as *Enterococcus faecium*, one strain as *Lactococcus lactis*, four strains as *Streptococcus pasteurianus*. Although, two strains (LEFS 42 and LEFS 55) showed a low 16S similarity (97.60% and 97.54% respectively) with the type strain *Streptococcus suis* 92-2742T. All the tested LAB strains possessed acidifying and proteolytic capacities. Most of them were weakly lipolytic and had the ability to produce exopolysaccharides. Besides, all the studied LAB strains exhibited antibacterial activity against Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi*) and Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus*) bacteria and sensitivity towards several antibiotics. *Streptococcus* sp. LEFS 55 showed the highest hydrophobicity, autoaggregation and coaggregation abilities. All the isolated strains were able to resist simulated human gastrointestinal tract conditions and *Streptococcus* sp. LEFS 55 showed the highest survival rate. Hence, LAB strains isolated from spontaneously fermented camel milk have the potential to be used as probiotics in fermented foods.

Key words: Fermented camel milk, lactic acid bacteria, identification, technological, probiotic.

Abstract N°: 48 (E -Poster 22)

THE POLYPHENOL/SAPONIN-RICH RHUS TRIPARTITA EXTRACT HAS AN APOPTOTIC EFFECT ON THP-1 CELLS THROUGH THE PI3K/AKT/MTOR SIGNALING PATHWAY

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Hyperactivation of mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) signaling pathway is involved in the regulation of cellular growth, proliferation, and more in general, is a common phenomenon in most types of cancers. Thus, natural substances targeting this pathway can be of great therapeutic potential in supporting the treatment of tumor patients. *Rhus tripartita* (Ucria) Grande is a plant growing in desertic areas which is traditionally used for the treatment of several diseases in Tunisia. In the present work, the biochemical profile of the main compounds present in the plant leaf extract was determined and the anti-leukemic potential of the plant extracts against acute monocytic leukaemia (AML) THP-1 cells was investigated. After HPLC identification of some phenolic compounds present in the plant extract and the quantification of saponin content, the cytotoxic effect of *Rhus tripartita* extracts on THP-1 cell culture was evaluated using the colorimetric MTT assay for cell viability. THP-1 cells were incubated with medium containing the relative IC50 concentrations of total plant extract, saponin extract and some standard compounds (rutin (R); kaempferol (K); mixture of catechin, epicatechin, and epicatechin-gallate (CEEG); ellagic acid (EA). Finally, qRT-PCR and western blotting analysis were used to evaluate the effect of some flavonoids present in a crude extract of polyphenols and the total extract of saponins on cell survival and apoptosis. Analysis of expression level of some gene (PIK3CA, PTEN, AKT1, mTOR, EIF4E, RPS6KB1, and TSC1) involved in the mTOR pathway and the phosphorylation of S6 and AKT proteins allowed to observe that a total *Rhus tripartita* extract and some of the compounds found in the extract controls THP-1 cell proliferation and apoptosis via regulation of the PI3K-AktmTOR signaling pathway. *R. tripartita* induced inhibition of cell cycle and induction of apoptosis may involve the mTOR pathway. Therefore, *R. tripartita* extract may be a useful candidate as a natural anti-cancer drug to support the treatment of AML.

Key words: *Rhus tripartita*, mTOR pathway, anticancer properties, Apoptosis, Leukaemia

Abstract N°: 49 (E -Poster 23)

POLYPHENOLIC PROFILE, ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY AND BRINE SHRIMP TOXICITY OF LEAF EXTRACTS FROM SIX TUNISIAN SPONTANEOUS SPECIES

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The aim of this study was to investigate the polyphenolic profile and biological properties of leaves acetonic extracts from six Tunisian spontaneous plants of *Marrubium vulgare* L., *Rhus tripartita* (Ucria) D.C., *Hernaria fontanesii* J. Gay subsp. *fontanesii*, *Ziziphus lotus* L., *Plantago ovata* Forsk., *Thymelaea hirsuta* (L.) Endl. Bioassay-guided and HPLC-PDA-ESI-MS procedures demonstrated that *R. tripartita* contained the highest amount of phenolic compounds (1475.1 mg/g), followed by *Z. lotus* (1087.8 mg/g) and *P. ovata* (1027.6 mg/g). Interestingly, in *R. tripartita* myricetin- 3-O-galactoside turned out to be the most abundant one. The plant extracts showed antimicrobial efficacy against *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. epidermidis* including methicillin resistant strains; no activity was detected against Gram-negative bacteria. *R. tripartita* revealed the best MIC and MBC values and caused significant decrease of *S. aureus* biofilm. Both *R. tripartita* and *Z. lotus* did not display any toxicity against *Artemia salina* Leach (LC50 > 1000 lg/mL).

Key words: Tunisian plant extracts; HPLC; phenolic compounds; antibacterial activity; biofilm; *Artemia salina* lethality bioassay

Abstract N°: 50 (E -Poster 24)

Cheese quality improvement using incorporation of essential oil of Thyme encapsulated. Suty of encapsulation effect

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The objective of this work was to study encapsulation effect on cheese quality improvement using essential thyme oil at different concentrations (0.5 ; 1 and 1.5 ml /kg) with LPS, on the quality of fresh cheese, through the evaluation of microbiological quality, physico-chemical parameters and organoleptic properties, during its storage at + 4±1°C for 18 days. Use of lactoperoxidase, a natural enzyme that is considered as an important element in the natural host defense system against bacterial infections. On the other hand, essential oils have different chemical composition profiles allowing them to be used as natural food preservatives Encapsulation is one of the techniques commonly used. It allows the immobilization of volatile compounds of essential oils, stabilizing the latter and protecting it from light, oxygen and temperature. Therefore, this process tends to protect and preserve the biological activities of these oils The purpose of encapsulation is to ensure the protection, compatibility and stabilization of an active ingredient in a formulation. Moreover, the latter can modify and control the release profile of an active substance to obtain, for example, a prolonged or triggered effect. This combination had a significant impact on all physicochemical parameters throughout the shelf life of the cheese. On the other hand, the incorporation of essential oil encapsulated with LPS had no significant effect on the texture. The combination of essential oil of thyme encapsulated with LPS showed that at the first day, The different concentrations had a significant effect on the microbiological quality compared to the control and LPS cheeses, but after nine days it was noted that only the concentrations of OEt of 1.5 and 1ml /kg had a significant impact on the microbiological quality of the cheese compared to other. On the other hand, the activation of LPS alone had no significant impact on the evolution of these germs (mesophilic aerobic germs, yeasts and molds and total coliforms). Regarding sensory analysis, no descriptor (color, odor, texture and overall acceptability) had a significant effect detected by the panel throughout the shelf life. These preservation combinations allowed an extension of the shelf life. In fact, the control cheese had an expiration date of 3.63 days and the one preserved by LPS only of 3.09 days. On the other hand, the combination of essential oil of thyme encapsulated with LPS allowed to increase the shelf life of fresh cheese by 4.19, 8.01 and 10.40 days respectively for OEt concentrations of 0.5, 1 and 1.5 ml/kg with LPS activation.

Keywords: cheese, microbiological quality, essential oil encapsulation, quality, shelf life.

Abstract N°: 51 (E -Poster 25)

Anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory beneficial effects of oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol olive leaf extracts in SK-N-SH neuroblastoma cells

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Olive tree extracts have a variety of health benefits due to their high phenolic content. This study investigated the potential anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory effects of olive tree leaf oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol-rich extracts in human SK-N-SH neuroblastoma cells. The cells were incubated with 1 to 100 μ M of each extract in presence of increasing concentrations of glucose (10 to 45mM). High glucose levels induced Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) production and inflammation in SK-N-SH cells. Both oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol reduced ROS production in SK-N-SH cells subjected to hyperglycemic conditions. This effect was more noticeable with hydroxytyrosol. Both extracts reduced the inflammatory responses induced by high glucose in SK-N-SH cells by decreasing the Interleukin 6 inflammation factor expression. In conclusion, oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol could be considered as promising drug candidates to diseases linked to oxidative stress and chronic inflammation such as diabetes or neurodegenerative diseases.

Key words: Oleuropein, Hydroxytyrosol, SK-N-SH cells, Oxidative stress, Inflammation.

Abstract N°: 52 (E -Poster 26)

Impact of instant controlled pressure drop (DIC) treatment on the technological quality of Deglet Nour Dates powder using Experimental Design

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Hot air drying may cause quality losses, especially for powder products. In this study, Instant Controlled Pressure Drop process has been proposed to intensify drying process. Indeed, this research is dedicated to evaluate the effects of DIC assisted drying process on dates powder quality. The texturing by Instant Controlled Pressure-Drop technology (DIC) of Deglet Nour Dates before convective hot drying was studied: Fresh dates samples were Instant Controlled Pressure Drop (DIC) treated under different conditions, i.e. saturated steam pressure (P) and treatment time (t), following a 2-factor/5-level Experimental Design. Treated fruits were dried at a temperature of 70°C and air velocity of 1.5 m/s in order to study the impacts of DIC on Deglet Nour dates powders. Color coordinates, water activity (Aw), moisture content, hygroscopicity, wettability, water solubility index (WSI), and total phenolic content of dates powder were determined.

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) confirmed that pressure was the most influencing parameter in terms of polyphenol content, color properties and physical properties of dates powder. Finally, DIC pre-treatment allowed the improvement of phenolic content retention and rheological behavior of dates powder compared to the untreated DIC samples.

Key words: Deglet Nour Dates powder; Drying; DIC; physicochemical quality; Experimental Design.

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Abstract N°: 53 (E -Poster 27)

Prickly pear molasses (*Opuntia ficus-indica* L.) attenuates bleomycin induced oxidative stress and lung fibrosis in rats.

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Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) is a chronic and progressive respiratory disease with limited treatment. IPF is characterized by fibroblasts proliferation and differentiation into myofibroblasts leading to extracellular matrix deposition and respiratory failure. We aimed to investigate in the present study the effect of prickly pear molasses (PPM) on an experimental model of pulmonary fibrosis induced by bleomycin (BLM) in *Wistar* rats. Animals were randomly divided into 5 groups of 8 rats each. Control group (G1), BLM group (G2), and 3 other groups (G3, G4 and G5) treated by a single intra-tracheal injection (4mg/kg) of BLM associated to standard diet mixed with PPM at 2%, 4.5% and 10% respectively, one week before BLM treatment and 3 weeks after. At the end of the protocol, all rats were sacrificed and lungs were extracted to evaluate fibrosis score and oxidative stress markers. Our phytochemical results revealed a large amount of polyphenols and flavonoids in PPM. Histopathological examination showed significant decrease in fibrosis score and collagen deposition in G4 and G5 compared to G2. We reported also that PPM modulates the disturbance in the level of antioxidant markers such as catalase, superoxide dismutase and malondialdehyde in G3, G4 and G5 compared to G2. In conclusion, this experimental study demonstrates that PPM can play antifibrotic and antioxidant activities due to the presence of large amount of bioactive polyphenolic molecules.

Key words: Prickly pear molasses, Pulmonary fibrosis, Oxidative stress.

Abstract N°: 54 (E -Poster 28)

Valorization of the cactus rackets fiber in the development of a bio-plastic: mechanical and thermal study

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Plastics are increasingly invading our environment. Every year, tons of plastic wastes are dumped into the environment. This could strongly affect the environment, human and animal health. For this, the substitution of plastics by new biodegradable and environment-friendly materials becomes a needful objective. In this context, our work aims to develop a new biomaterials based on biopolymers extracted from an agricultural bioresources. In fact, cactus rackets are an abundant plant bioresource, cultivated at a low cost and constitute a valuable source of functional biopolymers. The cactus rackets fibers have been extracted by gentle methods of green chemistry. Extraction yields were evaluated. A structural and microstructural study was made. The characterization of the obtained fibers by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR), X-ray Diffraction (DRX), Thermic Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) has shown that they are cellulosic fibers with high functional and thermal properties. These fibers have been used in the manufacture of fiberboard by thermal pressure. The results obtained prove that these fiberboards have interesting thermal and mechanical properties. These developed biomaterials constitute an interesting and promising alternative to bio-plastics and several applications could be imagined.

Key words: cactus rackets, fibers, biomaterials, mechanical and thermal properties.

Abstract N°: 55 (E -Poster 29)

Functional and nutritional properties of Pumpkin powders (*Cucurbita maxima*) resulting from an optimized process of Interval Starting Accessibility Drying

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Pumpkin is a multifunctional ingredient in the human diet, thanks to the high value nutrients that it contains. The pumpkin flesh is a rich source of primary and secondary metabolites, including carotenoids, tocopherols, essential vitamins, minerals ... The use of the fruit, especially in powder form obtained by drying, has increased to improve the nutritional value of foods. In this context the drying process becomes a key element in the preservation of its molecules and improvement of the powders properties. Thus, Interval Starting Accessibility Drying (ISAD) was applied to the pumpkin flesh with a succession of action time of 5s, energy input by convective air at 40°C, and a tempering time of 3 min. The powder obtained by ISAD was compared to the powder obtained by continuous (40°C) and freeze-drying (-60°C, 24h). Drying methods had a significant influence on the powder's functional properties. Indeed, ISAD has high water retention, greater swelling power, and a lower oil absorption. Water adsorption values for dried pumpkin powders produced with ISAD, continuous and freeze-drying mode were 16.08; 13.39 and 8.22g/g, respectively. Similarly, for swelling power, the ISAD has a higher index. The results show an increase of a* value for ISAD contrary to the parameter b* and L*, which could reflect the more pronounced red color of the samples. However, the total carotenoid value obtained by continuous drying is slightly high compared to ISAD drying. ISAD showed the best quality in terms of color and functional properties probably due to a less deteriorated structure during drying.

Key words: Interval drying, functional properties, pumpkin powder, ISAD